

The Effect of Recruitment and Job Satisfaction on Employee Turnover Intention Pt Kharisma Unggul Tangerang

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study was to identify how recruitment and job satisfaction partially and simultaneously affect turnover intention at PT. Kharisma Unggul Tangerang. The research method used in this study is a quantitative method, with an associative approach. The sampling technique used is the probability sampling technique with a saturated sampling method with a sample of 62 people. The data analysis method uses a simple linear regression test, multiple linear regression, correlation coefficient, determination coefficient, and partial hypothesis tests (T test) and simultaneous (F test). The results of this study indicate that: Recruitment has a negative and significant effect on employee turnover intention at PT. Jakarta Prima Cranes. This is evidenced by the correlation coefficient value of 0.816, the t count value of $-2.136 < t_{table} - 1, 671$ and a significance level of $0.037 < 0.100$. Job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on employee turnover intention at PT. Kharisma Unggul Tangerang. This is evidenced by the correlation coefficient value of 0.887, tcount value $-6.372 < t_{table} - 1, 671$ and significance level $0.000 < 0.100$. Recruitment and Job satisfaction have a negative and significant effect on employee turnover intention of PT. Kharisma Unggul. This is evidenced by the results of the multiple linear regression equation $Y = 64.277 - 0.626 X_1 - 0.201 X_2$. The fcount value is $120.720 > f_{table} 2.39$ and the significance level is $0.000 < 0.100$. And the correlation coefficient value is 89.6%.

KEYWORDS: Recruitment, Job Satisfaction, Turnover Intention

INTRODUCTION

The key to a company's success is to consider employees as one of the most valuable assets for the company. Employees in the company not only carry out daily operational tasks, but also contribute to innovation, company culture, and long-term growth. Employees bring valuable skills, knowledge, and experience, which enable the company to compete effectively in the market. In other words, employees are strategic resources that support the achievement of company goals and business sustainability. Human Resource Management is not only limited to recruitment or how to get quality human resources but more importantly, it is related to how the company can maintain the existence of existing human resources so that they continue to contribute and do not move or leave the company. One of the problems that often becomes an obstacle for companies related to human resources is the high turnover rate.

Based on data from HRD PT. Kharisma Unggul Tangerang in the last three years the number of employees who resigned from the company is still high, in 2022 there were 17 employees who resigned, in 2023 as many as 12 employees and in 2024 as many as 16 employees. A company that experiences high turnover will experience various negative impacts related to the decline in company performance, because the company loses experienced employees. Experienced in the sense of not only in technical terms but also related to knowing the ins and outs of communication, work culture, and how the company works which have their own characteristics. Therefore, turnover can cause serious problems for companies and organizations, especially if the employees who resign are skilled employees with knowledge, talent, and experience, or even if the employees hold key roles in the company's strategy. The high level of turnover experienced in a company requires proper handling so that the existing problems get the best solution. One of the factors that causes high turnover rates is the recruitment system. The recruitment system has an important role in determining the level of turnover in an organization. If the recruitment process is not effective, the following problems can arise, which contribute to high turnover rates. Recruitment that is done in a hurry without in-depth evaluation of the candidate's characteristics can result in employees who are less committed to the company and a mismatch between the candidate's skills, experience, or values and the company's needs and culture.

Based on Data Processing from PT. Kharisma Unggul Tangerang, it can be concluded that Internal Problems of limited candidates occurred more frequently in 2021 and conflicts of interest became the main issue in 2022, emphasizing the need for a more objective promotion policy while External Problems in 2022 showed an increase in cultural mismatch issues, reflecting the need for a more comprehensive selection process and High salary expectations became the main challenge in 2023, along with increasing

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competition in the labor market. In addition to recruitment, job satisfaction is a crucial factor that influences turnover rates in companies. Job dissatisfaction can make employees feel uncomfortable, unappreciated, or have no clear career prospects, prompting them to look for opportunities elsewhere.

Based on the Job Satisfaction Pre-Survey, it can be concluded that the positive aspects of Relationship with Superiors and Work Environment received positive assessments, with more than 70% of respondents agreeing and Appreciation and Support from Superiors were also quite good, with 68% of respondents feeling supported. Meanwhile, the Aspects that Need to be Improved Work-Life Balance and Career Development Opportunities received a higher level of dissatisfaction, with 60% of respondents disagreeing about time flexibility and 52% feeling they had less opportunity to develop.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Wirawan (2015: 133) defines recruitment as a process of attracting job applicants by utilizing recruitment methods to get applicants to take part in the selection process in an effort to fulfill HR needs. The process begins when the company needs new employees, until their applications are accepted. In order to carry out effective recruitment, companies need to provide continuous and accurate information about the qualifications and number of employees needed to carry out the company's functions and duties. Meanwhile, another definition of recruitment is a process that begins with the desire to occupy the position provided until the applicant submits his application documents (Andrian, Hamidah, & Yuniadi, 2017: 75). In this case, the accuracy of employee recruitment can be seen from the suitability of recruitment with employee planning. Every company needs employee recruitment to fill the job vacancies provided. Yuniarsih & Suwatno (2021: 102) state that recruitment is an activity to obtain several workers from existing sources, adjusted to the required qualifications, so that they are able to carry out the company's mission in order to realize its goals and vision. Recruitment is a series of activities carried out in a planned manner to obtain prospective employees who meet existing requirements (Suryadana, 2015: 52).

Job satisfaction is an individual's general attitude towards aspects of their work (Robbins & Judge, 2017). Job satisfaction includes cognitive, affective and evaluative responses or attitudes, feelings of pleasure or positive emotions that arise from the assessment of one's work or work experience. Job satisfaction is an individual's general attitude towards their work, the difference between the amount of compensation employees receive and the amount they feel they should receive. The more aspects of the job that are in accordance with the individual's desires, the higher the level of satisfaction. According to Robbins (2017:91) the term job satisfaction refers to an individual's general attitude towards the work they do. A person with a high level of job satisfaction will show a positive attitude towards their work, while someone who is dissatisfied with their work will show a negative attitude towards their work. According to Mangkunegara (2022:117) job satisfaction is a feeling that supports or does not support the employee's self related to their work and their condition. Employees will feel satisfied at work if aspects of the job and aspects of themselves support them and vice versa if these aspects do not support them, employees will feel dissatisfied. Basically, job satisfaction is an individual thing because each individual will have different levels of satisfaction according to the values that apply in each individual. The more aspects of the job that are in accordance with the individual's desires, the higher the level of satisfaction felt. Job satisfaction is an affective or emotional response to various aspects or aspects of a person's job so that job satisfaction is not a single concept. A person can be relatively satisfied with one aspect of the job and dissatisfied with one or more other aspects. (Indrasari, 2017:37) Meanwhile, according to Hasibuan (2023:202) Job satisfaction is an emotional attitude that is pleasant and loves his job. This attitude is reflected by work morale, discipline, and work performance. Job satisfaction is enjoyed in work, outside of work, and a combination of inside and outside of work. From the explanation above, it can be interpreted that job satisfaction is a form of positive attitude where the expected desires have been fulfilled which results in employees being more productive in carrying out their work. According to Tett and Meyer in Ardianto, R., and Bukhori, M. (2021) turnover intention is characterized by the emergence of a desire to leave work, look for a new job and look for a new profession. This is important for the company to know so that when these signs appear, the company is able to make a plan to deal with it so that turnover does not occur. Elmi (2018:205) argues that turnover intention is interpreted as the desire or intention of workers to leave the company. Turnover refers to the final reality faced by the company in the form of the number of employees who leave the company in a certain period, while turnover intention is the desire of employees to move referring to the results of individual evaluations regarding the continuation of the relationship with the company that has not been realized in the definite action of leaving the company. Based on several definitions from the experts above that turnover intention has similarities from these experts, it can be concluded that turnover intention is the desire of employees to leave their jobs due to several factors, one of which is because employees want to get a job elsewhere that is better than the job they are currently doing.

RESEARCH METHOD

According to Sugiyono (2017:147) who argues "in quantitative research, data analysis is an activity after data from all respondents or other data sources are collected: Activities in data analysis are grouping data based on variables and types, tabulating based on variables, presenting data based on the variables studied, performing calculations to answer the problem formulation, and

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performing calculations to test the hypotheses that have been proposed. The data analysis methods used in conducting this research are:

1. Data Instrument Test
 - a. Validity Test
 - b. Reliability Test
2. Classical Assumption Test
 - a. Normality Test
 - b. Multicollinearity Test
 - c. Autocorrelation Test
 - d. Heteroscedasticity Test
3. Descriptive Analysis
 - a. Simple Linear Regression Analysis
 - b. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis
 - c. Correlation Analysis
 - d. Determination Coefficient Analysis
4. Hypothesis Testing

In this study, the independent variables are recruitment and Job Satisfaction, while the dependent variable is Turnover Intention. So the author defines each variable and makes the variable operational.

According to Sugiyono (2022:38) defines the meaning of a variable as follows, anything in any form that is determined by researchers to study so that information is obtained, then conclusions are drawn. Meanwhile, the theoretical meaning of a variable according to Sugiyono, (2022:38) states that a research variable is an attribute or trait or value of a person, object, organization or activity that has certain variations determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions are drawn.

According to Sugiyono (2022:39) this variable is often referred to as a stimulus, predictor, antecedent variable. The independent variable is a variable that influences or causes changes or the emergence of the dependent variable. The independent variables in this study are:

- a. Recruitment (X1)
- b. Job Satisfaction (X2)

According to Sugiyono (2022:39) the dependent variable is a variable that is influenced or that is the result, due to the existence of an independent variable. The dependent variable or bound variable in this study is: Employee Turnover Intention

RESULTS

The characteristics of respondents in this study have four main characteristic categories: gender, age, last level of education, and length of service. The characteristics of the respondents in this study are described below.

- a. 62 respondents participated in this study. Of these, 35 respondents or 56.5% were male. Meanwhile, 27 respondents or 43.5% were female.
- b. 62 respondents participated in this study. Most of the respondents, namely 41 people or 66.1%, were in the age range of 20-29 years. A total of 16 respondents or 25.8% were in the age range of 30-39 years, and 3 respondents or 4.8% were in the age range of 40-49 years. Meanwhile, respondents who were in the age range of 50-59 years amounted to 2 people or 3.2%.
- c. 62 respondents participated in this study. The majority of respondents, namely 32 people or 51.6%, had a bachelor's degree. A total of 22 respondents or 35.5% had a high school/vocational high school education, and 7 respondents or 11.3% had a D3 education. Only 1 respondent or 1.6% has a Master's degree.
- d. 62 respondents participated in this study. The majority of respondents, namely 39 people or 62.9%, have work experience between 0 and 5 years. A total of 16 respondents or 25.8% have work experience between 6 and 10 years, and 6 respondents or 9.7% have work experience between 11 and 15 years. Only 1 respondent or 1.6% has work experience of more than 15 years.

This study involves classical assumption tests that include Normality, Multicollinearity, Autocorrelation, and Heteroscedasticity tests. The results of each type of classical assumption test are presented as follows:

Table I. Normality Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test	
	Unstandardized Residual
N	62
	Mean
	.0000000

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Normal Parameters ^{3,15}	Std. Deviation	2.63606676
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.072
	Positive	.047
	Negative	-.072
Test Statistic		.072
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.		
d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.		

Source: SPSS 25 Processing Data

From the test results in the table, it can be seen that the significance value achieved, which is more than 0.10, is 0.200. This shows that the distribution of the test data is considered normal.

Image I. Heteroscedasticity Test

Source: SPSS 25 Processing Data

The distribution of the points does not show a consistent or specific pattern. This indicates that there is no heteroscedasticity problem in the regression model being tested, which means that the model is reliable for use in research.

Table II. Multicollinearity Test

		Collinearity	
		Toleranc	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Rekrutmen	.285	3.512
	Kepuasan	.285	3.512

Source: SPSS 25 Processing Data

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value for the Recruitment (X1) and Job Satisfaction (X2) variables is 3.512, which is less than 10, and the Tolerance value is 0.285, which is more than 0.10. This indicates that there is no multicollinearity in the data, or in other words, the data is free from symptoms of multicollinearity.

Table III. Autocorrelation Test

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.896	0.802	0.796	2.680	2.293
a. Predictors: (Constant), Rekrutmen, Kepuasan Kerja					
b. Dependent Variable: Turnover Intention					

Source: SPSS 25 Processing Data

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The regression model tested is free from autocorrelation. This conclusion is supported by the Durbin-Watson number which reaches 2.293, indicating that the value is in the range of 1.55-2.46.

Table IV. Linear Regression Test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	64.277	1.834		35.044	.000
	Kepuasan Kerja	-.626	.098	-.691	-6.372	.000
	Lingkungan Kerja	-.201	.094	-.232	-2.136	.037

Source: SPSS 25 Processing Data

The regression analysis shown in table 4.20 produces a regression formula $Y = 64.277 - 0.626 X_1 - 0.201 X_2$. From the equation above, the following is the interpretation of the formula:

- 1) Intercept (Constant) = 64.277

This figure shows the value of Y (turnover intention) when the values of X1 (recruitment) and X2 (job satisfaction) are 0. In this context, if someone assesses the recruitment process as bad and has no job satisfaction at all (values $X_1 = 0$ and $X_2 = 0$), then turnover intention is predicted to be 64.277.

- 2) Coefficient X1 (recruitment) = -0.626

This coefficient shows the change in Y (turnover intention) for every one unit change in X1 (recruitment), assuming the value of X2 (job satisfaction) remains constant. Because the coefficient is negative, this means that there is a negative relationship between recruitment and turnover intention. Every one unit increase in recruitment will reduce turnover intention by 0.626 units, assuming constant work environment.

- 3) Coefficient of X2 (Job satisfaction) = -0.201

This coefficient shows the change in Y (turnover intention) for every one unit change in X2 (job satisfaction), assuming constant value of X1 (recruitment). Since the coefficient is negative, it means that there is a negative relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention. Every one unit increase in job satisfaction will reduce turnover intention by 0.201 units, assuming constant recruitment.

Table V. Correlation Coefficient Test Results

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.896 ^a	.802	.796	2.680

a. Predictors: (Constant), Rekrutmen, Kepuasan Kerja

Source: SPSS 25 Processing Data

Significance value less than 0.000 indicates a significant correlation. The r square value is 0.802, which is in the range of 0.800 - 1.000. This indicates that the relationship between recruitment variables (X1) and job satisfaction (X2) with turnover intention (Y) is very strong.

Table VI. Results of Determination Coefficient Test

Mod		el Summary		
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the
1	.896 ^a	.802	.796	2.680

a. Predictors: (Constant), Rekrutmen, Kepuasan Kerja

Source: SPSS 25 Processing Data

The value of the determination coefficient R Square (R²) was recorded at 0.802 or 80.2%. This indicates that the recruitment and

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job satisfaction variables together contribute 80.2% to the variability in turnover intention. Meanwhile, 20.8% of the variability is influenced by other factors not explained in this study.

Table VII. Partial Hypothesis Test Output Results Between Recruitment (X1) and Turnover Intention (Y)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	64.277	1.834		35.044	.000
	Rekrutmen	-.201	.094	-.232	-2.136	.037

Source: SPSS 25 Processing Data

Partial t-test analysis indicates that the resulting standard Beta Value is -0.232. This indicates that the Recruitment variable (X1) has a negative influence on turnover intention (Y). This means that the better the recruitment, the lower the employee's intention to leave the company.

Table VIII. Partial Hypothesis Test Output Results Between Job Satisfaction (X1) and Turnover Intention (Y)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	64.277	1.834		35.044	.000
	Kepuasan Kerja	-.626	.098	-.691	-6.372	.000

Source: SPSS 25 Processing Data

Partial t-test analysis indicates that the resulting standard Beta Value is -0.691, This indicates that the job satisfaction variable (X2) has a negative influence on turnover intention (Y). This means that the higher the job satisfaction, the lower the employee's intention to leave the company.

Table IX. Results of Simultaneous Hypothesis Test Output Between Recruitment (X1) and Job Satisfaction (X2) on Turnover Intention (Y)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1720.236	2	860.118	120.720	.000 ^b
	Residual	423.880	59	7.184		
	Total	2144.115	61			
a. Dependent Variable: Turnover Intention						
b. Predictors: (Constant), RekrutmenKepuasan Kerja						

Source: SPSS 25 Processing Data

The significance value for the influence of Recruitment (X1) and job satisfaction (X2) on turnover intention (Y) is 0.000 (less than 0.10). In addition, the f-count value of 120.720 is also greater than the f-table value of 2.39. Therefore, we can conclude that H03 is rejected and Ha3 is accepted. This means that Recruitment (X1) and job satisfaction (X2) have a simultaneous and significant influence on turnover intention on employees of PT. Kharisma Unggul Tangerang.

CONCLUSION

Recruitment has a significant and negative effect on employee turnover intention at PT. Kharisma Unggul Tangerang. This shows that the better the recruitment, the less a person's intention to leave their job will be. that Job satisfaction has a significant and negative effect on employee turnover intention at PT. Kahrisma Unggul Tangerang. The study shows that a higher level of job satisfaction is negatively correlated with an employee's desire to leave the company. Recruitment (X1) and Job Satisfaction (X2) have a significant effect on employee turnover intention at PT. Kharisma Unggul Tangerang. The study shows that the better the recruitment and the higher the job satisfaction, the lower the person's desire to leave their job. This shows that there is an inverse relationship between Recruitment and Job Satisfaction with the intention to leave the job.

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